

CREEP BEHAVIOUR OF EPOXY/CLAY NANOCOMPOSITE

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SUMMARY

In the current study the peculiarities of creep behaviour of epoxy/clay nanocomposite (NC) under effect of moisture are estimated. The viscoelastic properties of NC were investigated experimentally and their dependence on filler and moisture effect was determined. The obtained results of uniaxial quasistatic tensile tests and creep tests were compared and effect of moisture and filler on NC and matrix properties was analyzed.

Keywords: nanoclay composites, moisture effect, viscoelastic properties, creep, tension

INTRODUCTION

Recently several works have been devoted to the investigation of creep behaviour of NC such as polyamide 66 filled with TiO₂ nanoparticles [1-3], polyamide 6 filled with layered silicate [4], starch-polycaprolactone blend filled with montmorillonite modified by quaternary ammonium salt [5] and polypropylene filled with shorter and longer aspect ratio multiwalled carbon nanotubes [6]. Creep behaviour is rather important property of polymer composites that determines their dimensional stability especially in applications where material should support loads for a long period of time [5].

It has been shown in the literature that the use of polymers filled with exfoliated layered silicate platelets instead of unfilled polymers can give an advantage - appreciable improvement in creep resistance [4, 5]. Due to large length to thickness ratio and high stiffness of the particles, the optimal properties could be reached at lower filler content than with the use of traditional minerals or fibre fillers [5]. Nevertheless the effect of moisture on creep behaviour of polymer containing nanoparticles is still unclear and hardly published. Due to moisture absorption glass transition temperature T_g can be reduced below the operating temperature and this strongly increases the creep compliance [4].

Therefore the aim of current investigation is to estimate peculiarities of tensile quasistatic and creep behaviour of epoxy/clay NC under effect of moisture. The creep behaviour of this NC is of crucial interest because it is investigated also close to its glass transition temperature.

EXPERIMENTAL

Bisphenol A epoxy resin was used as a matrix of the composite. The filler was intercalated octadecylamine modified montmorillonite-based organoclay. The filler content was varied from 0 till 6% by weight.

Moisture sorption experiments [7, 8] were performed in atmospheres with relative humidity $\varphi = 24, 77,$ and 98% using desiccators with silica gel and saturated solution of salts NaCl and K_2SO_4 . The moisture kinetics was measured until specimens reached the saturation level. The average equilibrium moisture content for NC was app. -0.4, 1.7 and 3.2 % for $\varphi = 24, 77,$ and 98% with increase by app. 7 % for filler content changing from 0 to 6 % wt. At least four specimens of the same compositions were tested for each test. All the experiments were carried out at room conditions.

Quasi static tensile tests were performed with Zwick 2.5 at speed of 5 mm/min and creep tests at stress level equal to half of tensile strength for 7 h and recovery tests for 17 h for the specimens at room temperature. The decrease of tensile strength with increase of absorbed moisture content was taken into account. In order to estimate T_g of NC for all filler and moisture contents differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analysis was applied using Mettler Toledo DSC device for temperature range from -50 to 150°C at heating rate 10°C/min.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thermal analysis

Using DSC analysis glass transition temperature of moistened NC with different filler content was determined. The results of the effect of filler and moisture content on T_g are given in Fig. 1. As seen from this figure glass transition temperature of NC remains nearly constant within one atmosphere and is about $50\pm 0.4, 46\pm 0.5$ and 40 ± 0.4 °C in atmospheres with $\varphi = 24, 77$ and 98% RH.

Fig. 1. Glass transition temperature versus relative humidity of atmosphere of NC with different filler content (numbers on the curves).

The slight reduction of NC T_g with increase of clay content indicates a possible lower crosslink density around the clay particle, perhaps due to the perturbing effects of the clay [11, 12] or/and interaction between polymer chains with the surface of the particles and consequent interphase formation between the silicate layers [13, 14].

Since glass transition temperature of moistened NC is rather close to room temperature and temperature of mechanical tests of NC peculiarities for short- and long-term deformability is of current interest.

Quasistatic tensile tests

Experimentally measured stress-strain curves of NC with $c = 6\%$ moistened at $\varphi = 24, 77$ and 98% RH are shown in Fig. 2. From these curves it could be observed that the effect of moisture on mechanical behaviour is substantial. Absorbed moisture essentially plasticizes the NC and changes its fracture character from brittle in dry atmosphere to plastic one in wet atmospheres.

Fig. 2. Typical stress-strain curves at a fixed rate of deformation ($v = 5$ mm/min) for NC with $c = 6\%$ and $\varphi = 24, 77$ and 98% RH.

In order to examine the effect of organoclay content on mechanical properties, elastic modulus and tensile strength were plotted versus filler mass fraction (Fig. 3, 4). Tensile strength is defined as the maximal achieved value of stress in the specimen, and elastic modulus is calculated from the slope of a secant line between 0.05% and 0.25% strain on a stress-strain plot. It is clear from these figures that elastic modulus increases up to 20% and tensile strength of the NC decreases about the same value with the increase of organoclay content to 6% for atmosphere with 24% RH. The reduction of tensile strength in epoxy/clay systems could be attributed to the stress concentration effect of clay agglomerates [15]. The point is that non-exfoliated clay particles can form large agglomerates and as a result clay-matrix interactions decrease as clay content increase [15, 16]. In other words the reduction in interfacial interactions lowers the efficiency of the clay in strengthening of epoxy.

Fig. 3. Elastic modulus of NC in atmospheres with different relative humidity versus filler weight fraction.

Fig. 4. Tensile strength of NC in atmospheres with different relative humidity versus filler weight fraction.

Figures 3 and 4 also show the quantitative effect of moisture on tensile strength and elastic modulus of NC. Tensile strength of moistened composite drops twice. Elastic modulus both of moistened pure epoxy resin and NC is reduced approximately 1/3 in comparison to initial state.

Creep tests

Creep performance is commonly represented by creep compliance $J(t)$ and

$$J(t) = \frac{\varepsilon(t)}{\sigma},$$

where $\varepsilon(t)$ is creep strain and σ is applied stress.

For dry atmosphere and NC with different filler content the creep compliance curves are given in Fig. 5. As seen from the figure the inclusion of clay nanoparticles into epoxy resin led to a sufficient reduction of creep compliance of NC specimens dried in atmosphere of 24% RH. Nevertheless for humid atmospheres absorbed moisture significantly affected creep behaviour, leading to high deformability.

Fig. 5. Creep compliance curves of NC specimens saturated in atmosphere with 24% RH.

In Fig. 6 the creep curves for dried and moistened NC are superimposed on one reference curve by shifts along the time axis from the compliance curve obtained in dry atmosphere. The figure shows the reference curves for all filler contents. It can be seen that the curves have different shape. Obviously the creep compliance of NC in dry atmosphere is reduced in comparison with unfilled epoxy but with the increase of absorbed moisture content the plastization of the resin occurs (the mobility of polymer chains increases). The change of creep behaviour that led to increase of creep compliance with increase of filler content was possibly caused by morphological peculiarities of filler particles (the layered structure and the initial formation of aggregated stacks). Due to these factors the creep compliance could be increased by additional “sliding” of silicate nanoparticles within the layered stacks.

Fig. 6. Creep compliance for NC of different filler content (numbers on the curves) as a function of time. The overlapped curves represent the curves shifted over the time axis.

In order to estimate the effect of moisture on long-term deformability of NC the creep parameters should be clearly denoted. Fig. 7 shows a standard creep-recovery test with time-dependent deformation. The initial data obtained from creep curves are maximal deformation ε_{\max} , elastic deformation ε_{el} , viscoelastic jump ε_{vej} and residual deformation ε_{res} after recovery test.

Fig. 7. A standard creep-recovery test.

Further calculations provide additional data such as viscoelastic and plastic deformation $\varepsilon_{vel+pl} = \varepsilon_{max} - \varepsilon_{el}$, elastic recovery $\varepsilon_{el.rec} = \varepsilon_{max} - \varepsilon_{vej}$, viscoelastic relaxation

$\varepsilon_{vel.rel} = \varepsilon_{vej} - \varepsilon_{res}$, elastic modulus of composite at loading $E_l = \frac{\sigma}{\varepsilon_{el}}$ and unloading

$$E_{ul} = \frac{\sigma}{\varepsilon_{el.rec}}.$$

It is obvious from Fig. 2 that the stress level (0.5 of tensile strength) used for creep tests is relatively far from yield stress of the NC at room temperature. At this case the dominant deformation mechanism of the polymers during creep is assumed to be mainly viscoelastic if T_g of NC is higher than test temperature [2].

Fig. 8. Deformations - ε_{vel+pl} , $\varepsilon_{vel.rel}$ and ε_{res} versus filler content for atmosphere with 98% RH.

Since the most essential creep deformations were observed for NC specimens moistened in atmosphere with 98% RH, the special attention is given to estimate peculiarities of NC creep behaviour at these conditions. Fig. 8 shows the dependence of three creep parameters – viscoelastic plus plastic deformation, viscoelastic relaxation and residual (plastic) deformation on filler content. It can be observed that there is a good correlation between them. All the deformations increase with the increase of filler content till 6 %. Therefore it was confirmed that inclusion of clay nanoparticles to epoxy resin restricts the mobility of polymer chains in dry atmosphere and improves creep resistibility of the polymer, but absorbed moisture drastically plasticized the polymer (lowering T_g by 10 °C) and changed creep behaviour leading to the increase of creep compliance with the increase of filler content. Particularly high deformations were observed for the highest filler content in atmosphere with highest humidity which can be explained by additional “sliding” of silicate nanoparticles within the layered stacks.

Fig. 9. Elastic modulus versus filler content (symbols – results of creep tests, curves – results of quasistatic tensile tests).

The results for elastic modulus obtained from quasistatic tensile tests and creep tests are compared in Fig. 9. It should be noted that elastic modulus for creep and recovery experiments almost coincide. It can be seen that results of quasistatic tensile tests and creep tests resemble. Elastic modulus in these tests increases by app. 30 (25)% with increase of filler content and decreases by app. 45 (40)% with increase of moisture content. As it was shown and discussed before in both tests moisture significantly affects behaviour of deformation, leading to high deformability especially in atmosphere with 98% RH.

CONCLUSIONS

In the present paper the effect of moisture absorption on the quasistatic tensile and creep behaviour of epoxy/clay NC was examined. From the above investigation the following conclusions may be derived:

- Results of quasistatic tensile tests and creep tests resemble. Elastic modulus in these tests increases by app. 30 (25)% with increase of filler content and decreases by app. 45 (40)% with increase of moisture content. In both tests

moisture significantly affects behaviour of deformation, leading to high deformability especially in atmosphere with 98% RH.

- Particularly high deformations were observed for the highest filler content in atmosphere with highest humidity which can be explained by “sliding” of clay platelets induced by plasticization of epoxy resin.
- It has been experimentally testified that inclusion of nanoparticles to polymer restricts the mobility of polymer chains in dry atmosphere and improves creep resistibility of the polymer, but moisture drastically plasticized polymer (by lowering its T_g by 10 °C) and changed creep behaviour leading to increase of creep compliance with increase of filler content.
- The change of creep behaviour that led to increase of creep compliance with increase of filler content is possibly caused by morphological peculiarities of filler particles (the layered structure and the initial formation of aggregated stacks). Due to these factors the creep compliance could be increased by additional “sliding” of silicate nanoparticles within the layered stacks.

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